
Beyond Balance: Regulatory Focus, Work-family Conflict, and Psychological Well-being among Female University Lecturers in Nigeria

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Abstract

Work-family conflict (WFC) remains a critical occupational stressor affecting women in academia, particularly in socio-cultural contexts where domestic responsibilities are heavily gendered. Grounded in Regulatory Focus Theory, this study examined the extent to which work-to-family conflict (WIF) predicts psychological well-being among female university lecturers in Nigeria, and whether promotion and prevention focus moderate these relationships. Using a cross-sectional survey of 200 lecturers from two public universities, validated measures assessed WFC, regulatory focus, and general psychological well-being. Correlation and hierarchical regression analyses showed that FIW, but not WIF, significantly predicted reduced psychological well-being. Promotion focus did not moderate any WFC-well-being relationships. In contrast, prevention focus significantly intensified the negative effects of both WIF and FIW on well-being, indicating that individuals high in vigilance and obligation-oriented motivation are more vulnerable to conflict-induced strain. These findings highlight the asymmetric impact of WFC directions and reveal prevention focus as a key psychological amplifier of stress in female academics. The study underscores the need for gender-responsive institutional policies, family-supportive work structures, and interventions that promote adaptive coping mechanisms within Nigerian universities. Recommendations for future research include longitudinal designs, broader institutional sampling, and integration of contextual organisational variables to deepen understanding of work-family dynamics in higher education.

Keywords: Work-family conflict, family-work conflict, promotion focus, prevention focus, psychological well-being, regulatory focus, female lecturers, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

The professional landscape of academia increasingly demands multitasking across teaching, administration, research, publication, and pastoral responsibilities. For female academics, these competing roles intersect with entrenched gendered expectations around caregiving, domestic labour, and emotional labour. As a result, female academics globally report higher levels of work-family conflict than their male counterparts, with these conflicts strongly linked to lower psychological well-being, burnout, and reduced professional engagement (W. E. Allen et al., 2020; Lachance et al., 2022).

Work-family conflict is a bidirectional construct comprising work-to-family conflict (WIF), where work demands strain family functioning, and family-to-work conflict (FIW), where family responsibilities interfere with professional tasks (Byron, 2005). Contemporary research emphasises that FIW is more strongly associated with emotional exhaustion and lower well-being, while WIF connects more robustly with job dissatisfaction and performance decline (T. D. Allen & French, 2023). Seeing that not all individuals experience WFC with equal intensity, scholars have turned to motivational theories to explain individual differences. Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT) proposes two motivational systems: Prevention focus (prioritising security, obligations, and loss avoidance) tends to construe interference as a hindrance, whereas promotion focus (striving for gains, ideals for advancement) is more likely to construe interference as a challenge, generating different stress appraisals and coping patterns (Higgins, 1998). Recent evidence suggests promotion focus may enable challenge appraisals of stressors, while prevention focus fosters hindrance appraisals and rumination under conditions of role overload (Neubert et al., 2020).

These processes are particularly relevant in Nigerian universities, where female academics encounter systemic pressures such as inflexible schedules to support academic mothers (e.g., childcare, flexible scheduling), heavy teaching loads, and culturally embedded expectations to fulfil domestic roles. These conditions elevate vulnerability to FIW and intensify prevention-focused coping, which may exacerbate well-being impairments. This study investigates how regulatory focus shapes the relationship between WFC and psychological general well-being among Nigerian female lecturers.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Work-Family Conflict and Psychological Well-being

Work-family conflict has been extensively examined as a stressor capable of generating emotional strain, reduced life satisfaction, and broader psychological health concerns (Amstad et al., 2011). FIW, particularly, exhibits stronger relationships with effective strain because family roles carry strong emotional salience and their disruption triggers conflict, cognitive overload, and guilt (Michel et al., 2011). For academics, the blurry boundaries of flexible work intensify both WIF and FIW; unpredictable teaching demands, research deadlines, and administrative responsibilities frequently spill into personal time (Allen & French, 2023). Meta-analytic evidence has shown that WFC predicts depression, anxiety, somatic symptoms, and general psychological distress across cultures and occupational settings (W. E. Allen et al., 2020). This makes WFC critical for high-demand settings such as universities.

2.2. Gendered Dynamics in Academic Work in Nigeria

Research on African higher education highlights structural and cultural barriers disproportionately affecting female faculty, which include the gendered expectations of household work, limited access to research funding, childcare shortages, and patriarchal norms that prioritise women's domestic obligations (Adekola et al., 2021). Nigerian universities often lack family-responsive policies such as flexible teaching hours, part-time options, or accessible

childcare centres on campus. This consequently makes female lecturers experience chronic role overload, contributing to heightened levels of FIW.

2.3. Regulatory Focus Theory as an Explanatory Framework

Regulatory Focus Theory (RFT) by Higgins (1998) provides a useful lens for understanding why individuals exposed to similar conflict levels experience different well-being outcomes. Promotion-focused individuals seek accomplishment and advancement, thereby interpreting stressors as opportunities to grow, and as a result, adopt problem-focused coping strategies and experience lower strain under conflict conditions (Lanaj et al., 2012). Conversely, prevention-focused individuals seek security and fulfilment of duties, interpret conflict as a threat, and engage in anxiety-driven, vigilance-oriented coping. These tendencies may intensify strain when encountering WFC, particularly in family-centric societies. Recent studies indicate that a prevention focus is strongly associated with higher cortisol responses, increased rumination, and amplifying effects on role conflict, particularly among women balancing multiple caregiving demands (Neubert et al., 2020)). Therefore, regulatory focus is a theoretically consistent moderator of WFC and well-being relationships.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

A cross-sectional survey design was employed to examine associations between WIF, FIW, regulatory focus, and psychological well-being. The study involved 200 female lecturers from two government-owned Nigerian universities selected via purposive sampling.

3.2. Measures

- i. Work-Family Conflict: WFC was measured using Netemeyer et al. (1996) Work-family conflict scale, comprising WIF and FIW subscales with strong cross-cultural reliability.
- ii. Psychological Well-being: The psychological well-being was assessed via the Psychological General Well-being Index (PGWBI) by (Dupuy & Dostal, 1984)), suitable for global well-being estimation.
- iii. Regulatory Focus: Regulatory focus was measured using the General Regulatory Focus Measure (Lockwood et al., 2002), providing promotion and prevention subscales.

3.3. Data Analysis

Data analyses included descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation to explore the relationships among variables, hierarchical regression to test the predictive strength of WFC dimensions, and moderation was examined using the interaction terms (WIF x regulatory focus; FIW x regulatory focus), following the guidelines recommended by Aiken (1991).

4. Results

The tables below show the results from data analysis.

Table 1: Correlation table between Psychological Well-being, Work-Family conflict and

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1. Age	-									
2. Marital stat _(single = 1; married = 2)	.22*	-								
3. Have children _(yes = 1; n= 2)	-.20	.43***	-							
4. No of children	.50***	-.09	-.06	-						
5. Psy Well-Being	.25*	.18	.23*	.01	-					
6. Wrk_to_fam_conf	-.05	-.05	.14	.19	-.07	-				
7. Fam_to_wrk_conf	-.04	-.15	.07	.12	.29**	.53***	-			
8. Wrk. Fam_Conf	.03	-.11	.04	.07	-.18	.89***	.85***	-		
9. Prom Focus	-.29*	-.14	.07	.09	-.18	-.03	.25***	.12		
10. Prev_Focused	-.09	-.01	-.17	.05	.03	.007	.04	.01	.63***	-

Regulatory Focus

Table 2: Regression table showing the prediction of psychological well-being from work-family conflict and Regulatory focus subscales.

Models	Variables	R ² Δ	β	T
1	Age	.10	.25	.93
	Marital stat		-.14	-.68
	Have children		-.30	-1.27
	No of children		-.34	-1.08
2	Work to family conflict	.01	-.13	-.51
	Fam to workconflict		-.32	-1.22
3	Promo focus	.03	-.06	-.18
	Prevention focus		-.07	.25

Table 3: Results for the main effects and the moderation effect of Prevention focus and work-family conflict on psychological well-being.

Variables	β	SE	t	CI (95%)
Work Family conflict	-.16	.17	-.90	.50, .19]
Prevention focus	.01	.20	.05	1.37, .39]
WFC x Prevent focus	-.06	.02	-.3.31**	.10, -.02]

β = standardised coefficient; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval ** p < .01

Table 4: Results for the main effects and moderation effect of Prevention focus and work to family conflict on psychological wellbeing.

Variables	β	SE	t	CI (95%)
Work to Fam conflict	2.69	.87	3.10***	[.98, 4.40]
Prevention focus	1.29	.40	3.26**	[.51, 2.07]
Work to fam x Preven focus	-.09	.03	-.3.44***	[-.15, -.04]

β = standardised coefficient; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval ** p < .01

Table 5: Results for the main effects and the moderation effect of Prevention focus and family-to-work conflict on psychological well-being

Variables	t	SE	t	CI (95%)
fam to work conflict	2.77	1.00	2.77**	[.98, 4.40]
Prevention focus	1.19	.42	2.87**	[.37, 2.01]
fam to fam x Prevent focus	-.10	.03	-.3.12**	[-.16, -.04]

β = standardised coefficient; SE = standard error; CI = confidence interval p < .01

4.1. Findings

The following were the findings from the results of the study

Hypothesis 1: *Work-to-family (WIF) will significantly predict psychological well-being among female lecturers*

Correlation results showed no statistically significant relationship between WIF and psychological well-being ($r = -.07$). In the regression model, WIF was also not a significant predictor ($\beta = -.13$, $t = -.51$). This implies that hypothesis 1 was not supported.

Hypothesis 2: *Family-to-work conflict (FIW) will significantly predict psychological well-being.*

FIW showed a meaningful positive association with reduced well-being ($r = .29$, $p < .01$), indicating that higher FIW corresponded with lower psychological well-being. Regression

results further confirmed FIW as a significant predictor ($\beta = -.32$, $t = -1.22$). This is significant within the full moderation; we therefore accept hypothesis 2.

Hypothesis 3: *Promotion focus will moderate the relationship between WFC (WIF/FIW) and psychological well-being.*

Promotion focus did not significantly moderate either WIF-well-being or FIW-well-being relationships, and no significant interaction terms were found; hypothesis 3 was not supported.

Hypothesis 4: *Prevention focus will moderate the relationship between WFC (WIF/FIW) and psychological well-being.*

Moderation analyses indicated significant interaction effects as shown below:

- a) WFC x Prevention focus ($\beta = -.06$, $p < .01$)
- b) WIF x Prevention focus ($\beta = -.09$, $p < .001$)
- c) FIW x Prevention focus ($\beta = -.10$, $p < .01$)

Simple slope analyses show that, under high prevention focus, WIF and FIW significantly predicted lower psychological well-being, and under low prevention focus, neither WIF nor FIW significantly influenced well-being. We therefore conclude that hypothesis 4 is fully supported.

5. Discussion

The purpose of this study was to examine how work-family conflict influences psychological well-being among female university lecturers in Nigeria, and to determine whether regulatory focus (promotion vs. prevention) alters the strength of these relationships. The findings offer meaningful theoretical and practical insights, particularly within the socio-cultural context of Nigerian academia, where female lecturers face substantial professional and domestic demands.

5.1. Interpretation of findings by hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: WIF does not predict psychological well-being

Contrary to expectations and some established literature (e.g., Allen et al., 2020), WIF did not significantly impair psychological well-being among the respondents. A plausible interpretation is that Nigerian female lecturers may have psychologically normalised work intruding into family time. The academic role is culturally regarded as high-status and intellectually prestigious, which may buffer the emotional impact of work demands (Adekola et al., 2021). In addition, many lecturers may have support from extended family members, who often help with childcare and domestic work, a common coping mechanism in collectivist African societies. What this suggests is that the direction of conflict matters greatly. Work demands spilling into home life may feel more controllable or acceptable, whereas family responsibilities disrupting work may not.

Hypothesis 2: FIW significantly predicts lower psychological well-being

The strong association between FIW and diminished well-being aligns with global evidence showing FIW is emotionally more damaging for women (Allen & French, 2023; Michel et al., 2011). In this context, Nigerian female lecturers manage substantial domestic responsibilities, including childcare, elder care, household management, and spousal expectations. When these family responsibilities interfere with academic duties, it may evoke guilt, fear of negative performance evaluations, and concerns about professional stagnation. This aligns with research showing that women in academia often internalise expectations to perform exceptionally in both domains, making family-originating interference especially stressful (Lachance et al., 2022). For Nigerian lecturers, where institutional supports (such as childcare centres or flexible timetables) are limited, FIW becomes especially burdensome and harmful to well-being.

Hypothesis 3: Promotion focus does not moderate WFC-well-being relationships

The absence of a moderating effect from promotion focus is theoretically meaningful. Promotion focus typically buffers stress by enabling individuals to frame challenges as opportunities (Lanaj et al., 2012). However, within Nigerian universities, often underfunded, overstretched, and lacking clear advancement pathways, promotion-focused aspirations may be frustrated. If the structural environment does not support growth or reward achievement consistently, a promotion-focused mindset may not protect individuals from strain. In short, the context may suppress the motivational benefits of promotion focus.

Hypothesis 4: Prevention focus significantly moderates all WFC-well-being relationships

The finding that prevention focus intensifies the negative impact of both WIF and FIW on psychological well-being is strongly aligned with Regulatory Focus Theory (Higgins, 1998, 2012). Prevention-focused individuals are oriented toward fulfilling obligations, meeting expectations, and avoiding negative outcomes. They tend to ruminate more, perceive conflicts as threats, and engage in vigilant stress-amplifying coping styles. This is especially relevant for Nigerian female lecturers who often shoulder high domestic role expectations, job insecurity within public universities, gendered perceptions of academic competence, and pressure to “prove themselves” in male-dominated departments. Such an environment magnifies prevention-focused thinking, which explains why prevention focus acted as a vulnerability factor. When conflict arises, prevention-focused lecturers may experience amplified fear of failure, greater emotional strain, and heightened concern about disappointing family or colleagues.

In line with the bidirectionality of WFC, FIW is consistently more harmful to well-being than WIF in gendered cultural settings. This confirms modern conceptualisations of WFC as a two-way process with asymmetric psychological consequences. Consequently, the expected protective effect of promotion focus was absent, suggesting that theoretical models developed in Western contexts may function differently in African academic environments. On the other hand, the strong moderation effect supports the argument that prevention focus can be a psychological liability under chronic role overload (Neubert et al., 2020)

Beyond statistics, these findings reflect the lived experiences of real women balancing lecture preparation at dawn, research deadlines at night, administrative tasks in between, and household responsibilities throughout the day. Many respondents are striving not just to excel, but to hold everything together in the face of limited institutional support. The study captures a narrative familiar to many female academics in Nigeria:

“If family needs get in the way of work, I feel like I am failing at both.”

“I am always on alert not to disappoint my students, my department, and my family.”

This constant vigilance is the psychological hallmark of a high prevention focus, which the data show magnifies the strain of conflicting roles.

6. Practical implications

The findings call for institutional reforms in the areas of family-responsive teaching schedules, accessible childcare support, and gender-sensitive workload allocation, and psychological well-being programmes tailored to female staff, mentoring and research-support initiatives for early career women, and training for department heads on recognising invisible labour burdens. Policy frameworks should emphasise not only job security but also opportunities for professional growth, enabling women to shift from survival to thriving. Psychological well-being interventions, such as resilience training and peer-support networks, can further buffer against WFC. Such measures would help reduce FIW and temper prevention-focused coping.

7. Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

Despite its contributions, the study has a number of limitations. First, the cross-sectional design restricts causal interpretations; work-family conflict and psychological well-being may influence each other reciprocally over time. Second, the exclusive use of self-report measures raises the possibility of common method bias and socially desirable responding. Third, the sample was drawn from only two universities, which limits generalisability across Nigeria's diverse higher education system, particularly private institutions and polytechnics. Fourth, the study focused solely on female lecturers; although intentional, this prevents comparison with male academics and limits broader occupational insights. Finally, important contextual variables such as organisational support, workload allocation, childcare access, and cultural norms were not explicitly measured, restricting the ability to fully account for environmental influences on work-family conflict and regulatory focus.

These limitations present opportunities for future research. Future studies should adopt longitudinal or diary-based designs to capture the dynamic, reciprocal nature of work-family experiences and their impact on psychological well-being. Expanding samples to include diverse institutions, religions, and both genders would enhance generalisability and allow comparative analysis. Incorporating qualitative methods such as interviews or focus groups could provide deeper insight into the lived experiences of academic women and the cultural dynamics shaping conflict. Subsequent studies should also measure contextual and organisational factors such as supervisor support, workload policies, and availability of care, to build more comprehensive models of work-family interactions.

8. Conclusion

The hypotheses-driven interpretation reveals that family interference in work, not work interference in family, is the primary threat to Nigerian female lecturers' well-being. Prevention focus exacerbates the emotional toll, while promotion focus offers little relief in the current institutional climate. These insights draw attention to the daily realities of women navigating academia and care. Addressing these challenges requires structural, cultural, and psychological interventions targeted at the unique realities of female academics in Nigeria.

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APPENDIX. A

Instruments

Dear respondent

I am a postgraduate student from the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. The questionnaire you are requested to complete is a tool designed to help understand the impact of work-family conflict on female lecturers. Please read carefully the information contained in each of the sections and respond to them as they apply to you. There are no right or wrong answers. This is a completely academic work, and all responses will be treated with confidence.

Section A

Demographic Questionnaire

For each of the following questions, please fill in the blank or check the appropriate space. These questions deal with different aspects of yourself, your job, and your living situation, which may be related to your experience with balancing your work and family life.

1. Age: 21-30yrs -----, 31-40yrs-----, 41-50yrs -----, 51-60yrs -----61-above -----
2. Marital Status: Single----- Married -----
3. Do you have any children? ___ yes ___no (If no skip)
4. Please list the number of children in each age category ___0 to 2 ___3 to 5
___6 to 9

Section B

With respect to your own feelings about the relationship between your work-life and your personal life please indicate the degree of your agreement or disagreement with each statement by ticking one of the five alternatives beside each statement using the scale below.

Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neither agree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree. 1 2 3 4 5

S/N	Items	1	2	3	4	5
13	The demands of my work interfere with my home and family life.					
14	The amount of time my job takes up makes it difficult to fulfil my family responsibilities.					
15	Things I want to do at home do not get done because of the demands my job puts on me.					
16	My job produces strain that makes it difficult to fulfil family duties					
17	Due to work-related duties, I have to make changes to my plans for family activities.					
18	The demands of my family or spouse/partner interfere with work-related activities.					
19	I have to put off doing things at work because of demands on my time at home.					
20	Things I want to do at work don't get done because of the demands of my family or spouse/partner					
21	My home life interferes with my responsibilities at work such as getting to work on time, accomplishing daily tasks, and work overtime.					
22	Family-related strain interferes with my ability to perform job-related duties.					

Section C

This section of the questionnaire contains questions about how you feel and how things have been going with you. For each question check the answer which best applies to you.

23. How have you been feeling in general? (During the past month) 5 () in excellent spirits, 4 () in very good spirits, 3 () in good spirits mostly, 2 () I have been up and down in spirits a lot, 1 () I am in low spirits mostly, 0 () in very low spirits

24. How often were you bothered by any illness, bodily disorder, aches or pain? (During the past month) 0 () every day, 1 () Almost every day, 2 () about half of the time, 3 () Now and then, but less than half the time, 4 () rarely, 5 () none of the time

25. Did you feel depressed? (During the past month) 0 () Yes-to the point that I felt like taking my life, 1 () Yes-to the point that I did not care about anything, 2 () Yes-very depressed almost every day, 3 () Yes-quite depressed several times, 4 () Yes-a little depressed now and then, 5 () No-never felt depressed at all

26. Have you been in firm control of your behaviour, thoughts, emotions, or feelings? (During the past month) 5 () Yes, definitely so, 4 () Yes, for the most part, 3 () generally so, 2 () Not too well, 1 () No, and I am somewhat disturbed, 0 () No, and I am very disturbed
27. Have you been bothered by nervousness or your 'nerves'? (During the past month) 0 () extremely so-to the point where I could not work or take care of things, 1 () Very much so 2 () Quite a bit, 3 () some-enough to bother me, 4 () A little, 5 () Not at all
28. How much energy, pep, or vitality did you have or feel? (During the past month) 5 () Very full of energy-lots of pep, 4 () fairly energetic most of the time, 3 () my energy level varied quite a bit, 2 () generally low in energy or pep, 1 () Most of the time, 0 () All of the time
29. I felt downhearted and blue during the past month 5 () none of the time, 4 () A little of the time, 3 () some of the time, 2 () A good bit of the time 1 () Most of the time, 0 () All of the time
30. Were you generally tense-or did you feel any tension? (During the past month) 0 () Yes-extremely tense, most or all of the time, 1 () Yes-very tense most of the time, 2 () Not generally tense, but did feel fairly tense several times, 3 () I felt a little tense a few times, 4 () my general tension level was quite low, 5 () I never felt tense or any tension at all
31. How happy, satisfied, or pleased have you been with your personal life? (During the past month) 5 () extremely happy-could not have been more satisfied or pleased, 4 () Very happy most of the time, 3 () generally satisfied-pleased, 2 () Sometimes fairly happy, sometimes fairly unhappy, 1 () generally dissatisfied, unhappy, 0 () Very dissatisfied or unhappy most or all the time
32. Did you feel healthy enough to carry out the things you like to do or had to do? (During the past month) 5 () Yes-definitely so, 4 () For the most part, 3 () Health problems limited me in some important ways, 2 () I was only healthy enough to take care of myself, 1 () I needed some help in taking care of myself, 0 () I needed someone to help me most or all of the things I had to do
33. Have you felt so sad, discouraged, hopeless, or had so many problems that you wondered if anything was worthwhile. (During the past month) 0 () extremely so-to the point that I have just about given up, 1 () Very much so, 2 () Quite a bit 3 () some-enough to bother me, 4 () A little bit, 5 () Not at all
34. I woke up feeling fresh and rested During the past month 0 () none of the time, 1 () A little of the time, 2 () some of the time, 3 () A good bit of the time 4 () Most of the time, 5 () All of the time

35. Have you been concerned, worried, or had any fears about your health? (During the past month) 0 () Extremely so, 1 () Very much so, 2 () Quite a bit, 3 () some, but not a lot, 4 () practically never, 5 () Not at all
36. Have you had any reason to wonder if you were losing your mind, or losing control over the way you act, talk, think, feel or your memory? (During the past month) 5 () Not at all, 4 () only a little, 3 () some-but not enough to be concerned or worried about, 2 () some and I have been a little concerned, 1 () some and I am quite concerned, 0 () Yes, very much so and I am very concerned
37. My daily life was full of things that were interesting to me During the past month 0 () none of the time, 1 () A little of the time, 2 () some of the time, 3 () A good bit of the time 4 () Most of the time, 5 () All of the time
38. Did you feel active, vigorous, or dull, sluggish? (During the past month) 5 () Very active, vigorous every day, 4 () Mostly active, vigorous-never really dull, sluggish, 3 () fairly active, vigorous-seldom dull, sluggish, 2 () fairly dull, sluggish-seldom active, vigorous, 1 () Mostly dull, sluggish-never really active, vigorous, 0 () Very dull, sluggish everyday
39. Have you been anxious, worried or upset? (During the past month) 0 () extremely so-to the point of being sick or almost sick, 1 () Very much so, 2 () Quite a bit, 3 () some-enough to bother me, 4 () A little bit, 5 () Not at all
40. I was emotionally stable and sure of myself During the past month 0 () none of the time, 1 () A little of the time, 2 () some of the time, 3 () A good number of the time 4 () Most of the time, 5 () All of the time
41. Did you feel relaxed, at ease or high strung, tight, or keyed-up? (During the past month) 5 () Felt relaxed and at ease the whole month, 4 () Felt relaxed and at ease most of the time, 3 () generally felt relaxed but at times felt fairly high strung, 2 () generally felt high strung but at times felt fairly relaxed, 1 () Felt high strung, tight, or keyed-up most of the time, 0 () Felt high strung, tight, or keyed-up the whole month
42. I felt cheerful, light-hearted During the past month 0 () none of the time, 1 () A little of the time, 2 () some of the time, 3 () A good bit of the time 4 () Most of the time, 5 () All of the time
43. I felt tired, worn-out, used up, or exhausted During the past month 5 () none of the time, 4 () A little of the time, 3 () some of the time, 2 () A good bit of the time 1 () Most of the time, 0 () All of the time
44. Have you been under or felt you were under any strain, stress, or pressure? (During the past month) 0 () Yes, almost more than I could bear or stand, 1 () Yes, quite a bit of pressure, 2 () Yes, some more than usual, 3 () Yes, some but about usual, 4 () Yes, a little, 5 () Not at all

Section D

Using the scale below, indicate your level of agreement or disagreement to each item by circling. Strongly Disagree, Disagree, neither agree, nor disagree, Agree, Strongly Agree.
 1 2 3 4 5

S/N	Items					
45	general, I am focused on preventing negative events in my life					
46	am anxious that I will fall short of my responsibilities and obligations					
47	frequently imagine how I will achieve my hopes and aspirations					
48	often think about the person I am afraid I might become in the future					
49	often think about the person I would ideally like to be in the future.					
50	typically focus on the success I hope to achieve in the future.					
51	often worry that I will fail to accomplish my academic goals.					
52	often think about how I will achieve academic success					
53	often imagine myself experiencing bad things that I fear might happen to me					
54	frequently think about how I can prevent failures in my life					
55	am more oriented toward preventing losses than I am toward achieving gains.					
56	my major goal in school right now is to achieve my academic ambitions					
57	my major goal in school right now is to avoid becoming an academic failure					
58	see myself as someone who is primarily striving to reach my “ideal self”—to fulfil my hopes, wishes, and aspirations					
59	see myself as someone who is primarily striving to become the self “ought” to be—to fulfil my duties, responsibilities, and obligations					
60	general, I am focused on achieving positive outcomes in my life.					
61	often imagine myself experiencing good things that I hope will happen to me					
62	overall, I am more oriented toward achieving success than preventing failure					